

Original Research

Investigating the Contribution of Different Types of Red Meat Consumption on Air Pollution in Iran

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Abstract

Since the production and consumption of meat are known to be among the leading causes of greenhouse gas emissions and environmental pollution, this study examines the relationship between the consumption of various types of red meat by households and its impact on air pollution and environmental contamination in Iran. For this purpose, this article tests this relationship using annual time series data from 1980 to 2019 and the FMOLS method. The findings indicate that the consumption of red meat has a negative effect on environmental pollution because it leads to air pollution and increases environmental pollution. According to the results, the consumption of cow and veal meat has a greater contribution on air pollution and environmental pollution, and the consumption of camel meat has the lowest contribution. Furthermore, the growth of consumption, which leads to the development of production in the economy, can result in air and environmental pollution, as meat production is an energy and input-intensive process. In light of these findings, policymakers must focus on controlling household consumption and production of these products by implementing tax and incentive policies to decrease environmental pollution.

Keywords: Air and Environmental Pollution, Consumption, Household, Red Meat.

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Introduction

According to the traditional rural structure, the main source of red meat is light livestock, and a large part of the consumers prefer it to heavy livestock (cow) in such a way that every year the important production of light livestock in the production of milk and beef is in a downward trend. Therefore, taking into account the taste of consumers, big cities are also inclined to consume beef (Nikokar, 2003).

Access to food and the ability to purchase these items are significant in determining the nutritional status of society and individuals. As such, it is the duty of the governments to ensure the supply of necessities and the minimum food basket of the people according to the level of public income by carrying out measures such as the implementation of support policies for the agricultural sector.

Therefore, the government has an important role in the occurrence of fluctuations and pricing of products, therefore, identifying the factors that cause changes in the price of agricultural products is of great importance, it will definitely help to improve policies in the agricultural sector. One of the characteristics of developing countries is the existence of fluctuating exchange rates, the reason for the fluctuations in the prices of developing countries can be large changes in the existence of exchange rates in combination with poor transmission resulting from inefficient infrastructure. (Harley (1996) and Liefert and Sedik and Serova and Koopman and Melyukhina. (1996).

Supporting the farm sector helps increase the efficiency of producers and consumers in producing and consuming agricultural products, which positively impacts productivity. However, most developing countries, including Iran, have been influenced by various government interventionist policies aimed at supporting the agricultural sector, affecting the price and market of these products. Price fluctuations in products such as red meat have put significant pressure on producers and consumers in the low class of society, thereby affecting the productivity of the entire production factors of the agricultural sector. Therefore, policymakers must select appropriate policies and support the farm sector, which will improve the efficiency of producers and consumers in the production and consumption of agricultural products (Motaghi, 2017)).

Recent years have revealed the risks and environmental damages resulting from the production and consumption of food products due to population growth, economic growth, energy consumption, urbanization, and industrial activities. Energy consumption is necessary for all economic and social activities, but excessive consumption results in environmental damage. Global warming and climate change have also led to worldwide concern, causing significant changes in natural ecosystems and increasing water levels, threatening the 50% of the world's population living in coastal areas (Fodha and Zaghdoud, 2010).

Meat is an essential food item, as it contains a higher amount of protein than vegetable protein and has a large number of amino acids necessary for the body, making it an essential source of energy and protein (Shahnavazi and Ashrafi, 2022), (Dastagiri, 2004), (Engstrom et al., 2007).

Meat is considered one of the vital goods and has therefore caused investment and planning in its production. In Iran, meat animals' production and breeding conditions are favorable, owing to geographical location, availability of different livestock breeds, and other environmental conditions. However, the breeding of these animals is often traditional and low-yielding.

The growth of population and meat consumption can be one of the factors affecting environmental pollution as an economic issue, with most experts agreeing that this factor plays a critical role in the creation and spread of pollution. Population growth and the increase in demand for meat products are of particular importance, with investigations of the economic effects of pollution caused by meat production on the environment being of great importance to the international community (Mosannen Mozafari and Sabuhi, 2013), (Salami et al., 2012), (Nasir and Rehman, 2011).

One of the foremost management challenges for countries today is the pollution resulting from greenhouse gases, which stem from human activities such as the production, supply, and consumption of meat, deforestation, and increased air pollution. Such actions have significant long-term implications on human well-being and life. The output of greenhouse gases and industrial waste, coupled with environmental pollution resulting from meat production for consumption, have led to a surge in environmental pollution, making its investigation imperative. Pollution has become a ubiquitous and dangerous phenomenon due to the growth of societies and the need to produce more meat to cater to increasing consumer demands. This concern is particularly pronounced in developing countries with economic development as one of the main goals of their planning, underscoring the need to investigate the adverse effects of pollution on the environment. This has effectively made environmental pollution and meat production mutually dependent on consumer products.

Red meat, including beef, mutton, and veal, is among the largest and most influential food classifications. The protein ratio of meat is higher than that of vegetable protein, making its qualitative value essential and a significant energy source for the body. Numerous studies have investigated the share of meat in the costs of urban and rural communities. Notably, in rural areas, most consumption comes from their own products. The high price of red meat and low income of rural households compared to urban homes result in lower consumption of red meat.

The consumption of red meat by households in Iran is one of the sources of pollution. Due to different consumer goods and services in society, this issue has become a significant concern in recent decades in developing countries, especially Iran. The emission of greenhouse gases that cause global warming, climate change, and environmental pollution in the agricultural sector's resources should be considered.

Investigating the role and impact of meat production and consumption on environmental pollution, and studying their relationship in countries like Iran, which are moving towards industrialization, is crucial as it could lead to significant ecological changes. Governments have consistently sought to examine the role and effects of environmental pollution to increase awareness and develop optimal policies to control it. Depending on the prevailing economic conditions, governments can improve social

welfare and control ecological pollution by establishing rules and policies that support better meat production while minimizing environmental pollution. therefore, according to the importance and content, the current paper is categorized into four sections. After the introduction, in the second section, materials and methods are introduced. In the third section, the results and discussion will be essayed and the conclusion of the findings will be illustrated in the fourth section.

Literature Review

This research aims to describe existing relationships and foundations in economic literature and estimate and analyze equations using Iran's financial data to derive conclusions and recommendations. The animal husbandry sector in agriculture has unique characteristics compared to other agricultural industries, such as cultivation and horticulture, requiring specialized plans and policies for its development. To create a suitable platform for animal husbandry industry growth, it is necessary to consider the variables that affect supply and demand both inside and outside the animal husbandry industry when developing government policies. This attention is critical for the industry to achieve its developmental goals. However, most animal husbandry research has examined supply and demand equations for meat separately (Zaman et al., 2012), (Akboostanci et al., 2011), (Van Der Weele et al., 2019), (Alston et al., 1999), (Hoekstra et al., 2006), (Abadie et al., 2016).

Using panel data, Selden and Song (1994) investigated the relationship between pollution caused by CO₂ and the gross domestic product (GDP) of 130 countries between 1951 and 1986. This research demonstrated that the Kuznets hypothesis had been confirmed up to a certain income level in the countries examined (Selden and Song, 1994).

Khanna (2002) studied the relationship between average household income and air pollution in several states in America. In addition to the average income of households, other exogenous variables, such as population, active labor force, unemployment, educated population, factory worker population, housewives, and the number of rented houses, were examined in Hanna's research (Khanna, 2002).

In recent years, many researchers have focused on the relationship between energy consumption, economic growth, and environmental issues. Stern (2004) suggests that energy consumption is a valuable indicator for evaluating environmental problems (Stern, 2004).

Alam et al. (2007) investigated the influence of ecological pollution determinants in Pakistan between 1971-2005. They found that an increase in gross domestic product and intensity of energy use results in environmental pollution.

Similarly, Soytaş et al. (2007) studied the relationship between energy consumption, income, and carbon emissions in the United States. They concluded a positive relationship between carbon emissions and energy consumption.

In China, Lau et al. (2009) investigated the most significant carbon dioxide emissions in 36 industries between 1998-2005. They found that avoiding investment in industries that cause more pollution can help reduce environmental pollution.

Jalil and Mahmoud (2009) studied the long-term relationship between air pollution and income in China between 1975-2005 and used the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) method to confirm the Kuznets hypothesis.

Yeong-Sheng (2009) in research using simple forecasting methods and mathematical models for economic forecasting and management of Malaysian meat consumption, the result shows that the consumption of beef and mutton plays an essential role in the food basket.

In the context of food consumption, Mozayani et al. (2014) used the Kuznets environmental curve to investigate the relationship between per capita income, control variables, and environmental quality. The study found a positive relationship between per capita income and carbon dioxide emissions in countries with low per capita income and medium to low per capita income and a negative relationship between per capita income and carbon dioxide emissions in countries with high per capita income and medium to high per capita income.

Sall et al. (2015) evaluated the environmental effects and the impact of taxes on the consumption of milk and meat in Sweden. The study found that most meat and some dairy products have high-income elasticity and that the simultaneous imposition of taxes on these products can reduce greenhouse gases.

Hunter et al. (2016) suggested that creating awareness and fear among consumers about the impact of meat consumption on climate change can be an effective way to reduce meat consumption and thereby reduce environmental pollution.

Martinez et al. (2019) studied the nitrogen produced in cities, which threatens the environment and changes its natural cycle. The results of the study suggest that citizens can have a significant effect in reducing nitrogen by making the right food choices.

In addition, Tamazian et al. (2019) evaluated the impact of the financial development index on pollution and found that economic development can cause more investment in environmental research.

Materials and Methods

In this research, the FMOLS method is used, which performs two corrections on the "OLS" method, which are A Bias Correction and An Endogeneity Correction. This method makes it possible to estimate the parameters of a co-accumulative equation and it has features like Super Consistent, Asymptotically Unbiased and Asymptotically normalized, which allows statistical inferences to be made.

In this research, the modified least squares method examines the relationship between types of red meat as independent variables and environmental pollution as a dependent variable. Examining the relationship between the types of red meat consumed by

households and environmental pollution is presented in the form of the following equation:

$$EP = \alpha_1 GB + \alpha_2 BBGH + \alpha_3 GVG + \alpha_4 GMBGM + \alpha_5 SHBSH + \varepsilon_i$$

Table 1. Description of variables

Variables	Description
EP	Environmental Pollution
GB	Mutton and Lamb
BBGH	Goat
GVG	Cow and Veal
GMBGM	Buffalo
SHBSH	Camel

One important aspect of dietary classification is the consumption of red meat. Red meat contains a higher protein ratio than vegetable protein, and its consumption constitutes a significant energy source for the body. However, red meat consumption is also associated with air and environmental pollution. Therefore, policymakers need to investigate the behavior of consumers to control red meat consumption and reduce air and environmental pollution. To estimate the relationships between meat consumption and environmental pollution, it is essential to ensure the stationarity of the variables. In the following table, the results of the ADF test are reported.

Table 2. Augmented Dickey-Fuller Unit Root Test

Variable	T-Statistic (Prob)	Degree of non-stationary
EP	-6.214828 (0.0000)	I(1)
GB	-4.694642 (0.0004)	I(0)
BBGH	-3.420966 (0.0148)	I(0)
GVG	-7.696480 (0.0000)	I(1)
GMBGM	-6.342302 (0.0000)	I(1)
SHBSH	-3.469597 (0.0129)	I(0)

The table results indicate that variables GB, BBGH, and SHBSH are stationary and variables EP, GVG and GMBGM are non-stationary and are an integrated process of degree one, which will become stationary variables with one differentiation.

Results and Discussion

In the following table, the results of the estimation coefficients of the equations are reported.

Table 3. Results of Model Estimation

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Statistic	Prob
GMBGM	0.017810	0.113618	1.567621	0.1245
GB	0.209464	0.107788	1.943286	0.0578
BBGH	0.159422	0.054745	2.17846	0.0000
GVG	0.490579	0.056794	3.637861	0.0000
SHBSH	0.005657	0.048219	0.117325	0.9072

The value of R², which represents the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that is predictable from the independent variables, is equal to 0.961267, indicating that the independent variables can explain 96% of the changes in the dependent variable.

The independent variable of sheep and lamb consumption has a significant and positive effect on the level of environmental pollution. Its coefficients are equal to 0.20, which shows that a one percent increase in the consumption of mutton and lamb meat causes a 0.20 percent increase in the amount of pollution. The independent variable of goat and goat meat consumption has a significant (direct) effect on the level of contamination. Its coefficient is equal to 0.15. The independent variable of beef and veal consumption has a significant and direct effect on the amount of pollutant emission. Its coefficient is equal to 0.49, which shows that a one percent increase in the consumption of beef and veal is equal to a 0.49 percent increase in the amount of pollution. The independent variable of consumption of buffalo meat has very little effect on the level of environmental pollution. The independent variable of consumption of camel meat also has a very small direct effect on the amount of pollution. The important point is that the share of the household's consumption bundle of buffalo and camel meat is low, and for this reason, the estimated coefficients of these variables are very low.

generally, the study results indicate that mutton and lamb consumption, goat meat consumption, and beef and veal consumption significantly and positively affect environmental pollution. In contrast, consuming buffalo and camel meat has an insignificant or negligible impact on environmental pollution. The estimated coefficients of these variables are also extremely low due to the expected share of their household consumption bundle.

The relationship between air pollution and the consumption and production of meat has been studied extensively. It is well established that the growth in meat production caused by increased consumption significantly contributes to greenhouse gas emissions. Moreover, the change in consumption and production requires energy consumption and inputs, leading to environmental pollution. Given these concerns, policymakers should focus on increasing the efficiency and productivity of using production inputs to reduce environmental pollution while maintaining economic growth.

The increasing density of greenhouse gases in the earth's atmosphere has heightened international concern and pressure to reduce and control their emission. In Iran, per capita, greenhouse gas emissions have risen, indicating the need for new tax and environmental policies to protect the environment. One strategy could be to control the consumption of goods such as meat, which contributes to household pollution. The use of environmental tax within the country's tax system can be an effective means of reducing pollution. In particular, applying an ecological tax to mitigate and control meat consumption may be one of the most important measures to reduce the environmental effects caused by greenhouse gas emissions from meat production and consumption.

Finally, in general, it can be said that the consumption of red meat by households has an effect on air pollution and the environment, and the contribution of red meat consumption on air pollution from the highest amount to the lowest amount is equal to cow and veal meat, mutton and lamb, goat meat, buffalo meat and camel meat, respectively.

Conclusions

Red meat plays a significant role in the consumption and cost of household goods. The increase in demand and population has led to a rise in the consumption and production of red meat and changes in its economic and social effects on society. The value of red meat is of particular importance among urban and rural residents, as evidenced by the share of meat in the expenses of these communities. However, the production of red meat is a significant source of greenhouse gas emissions, which cause environmental pollution, climate change, and global warming. To address the factors affecting environmental pollution, it is essential to understand that economic growth requires using natural resources and energy, which can lead to decay. Therefore, consuming sheep, lamb, cow, calf, camel, goat, and buffalo meat contributes to air and environmental pollution. Finally, in general, it can be said that the consumption of red meat by households has an effect on air pollution and the environment, and the contribution of red meat consumption on air pollution from the highest amount to the lowest amount is equal to cow and veal meat, mutton and lamb, goat meat, buffalo meat and camel meat, respectively. Given this connection between environmental pollution and meat production, measures should be taken to reduce the consumption of red meat and replace it with other protein sources, such as white meat, fish, and shrimp. Moreover, households' consumption bundles should be modified to include other protein-containing products such as eggs and cereals. To achieve environmental goals and reduce greenhouse gas production, consumption taxes should be used as a tool. Moreover, taxes and incentives should be implemented to reduce the external costs of damages caused by environmental pollution and to reduce pollution to a stable level. Taxes imposed on meat production and consumption industries based on the amount of waste they generate can help increase environmental information, accurately measure these wastes, and protect the environment. Therefore, policymakers should implement tax policies that discourage the consumption of red meat while encouraging the use of environmentally friendly protein sources to protect the environment and promote public health.

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